

Arctic Roadmap for Observing and Data Systems (ROADS)

Practitioner's Handbook

Part II

Deliberative draft for the 2026 Arctic Observing Summit

A product of the Arctic ROADS Advisory Panel.

Text and Diagrams are under deliberation; please contact info@roadsadvisorypanel.org with your comments and questions

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Arctic ROADS Handbook Part II

Putting the ROADS Process into Practice

0. Introduction

Part II of the Arctic ROADS Handbook is a practical guide for those carrying the process forward—especially Expert Panel (EP) *facilitators* who are there to guide their EP through the Integrated Advisory Process. It also serves as a key reference for Advisory Panel (AP) members, particularly those serving in the role of *champion* for any given EP. Together they form a bridge between the detailed, place-based subject matter expertise of EP members and the intentions of the ROADS process.

This Handbook provides step-by-step guidance, tools, and examples from early pilot efforts to support collaborative action focused on shared benefit. This guidance affirms that Arctic ROADS is intentionally flexible: EPs can begin modestly, adapt recommended practices, and grow as relationships deepen. That flexibility is matched by a call for rigor that each stage remains open, inclusive, and grounded in the needs and knowledge of those who will use and benefit from the results. Through each phase of the process, all engaged form a learning loop that strengthens each round of planning.

Throughout this work, transparency and reflection are essential. Plans, decisions, and lessons learned should be documented and shared via the ROADS Process Workbook, so others can build on them.

All references to the Process Workbook point to [live templates hosted in Google Docs](#), which can be copied for direct use.

0.1 Applying the Guiding Principles Across the Integrated Advisory Process

The Guiding Principles are not just abstract values; they are the framework through which the AP evaluates EP progress at every stage of the Integrated Advisory Process. To ensure alignment and accountability, EPs must demonstrate how these principles inform their structure, dialogue, and technical outputs. Rather than viewing these as static requirements, EPs should treat them as an iterative lens that sharpens as the work moves from initial formation (Phase I) to implementation planning (Phase IV).

1. Inclusion

This principle calls for EPs to foster a community of practitioners that spans scientific, Indigenous, and practitioner knowledge systems, regions, cultures, and professional roles—including community leaders, researchers, data managers, and funders. This

principle is most critical during Phase I, where the EP must establish itself as a body that is prepared to engage a broad range of input. The AP recognizes that inclusion is closely linked to the scope of the effort as defined in the documentation. As the process moves forward, the principle ensures that prioritized benefits and technical requirements reflect the full range of expertise within the group, preventing the design from becoming siloed or overly narrow. Communication and engagement plans provide transparency and structure around inclusion, which is why these are included in the requested documentation.

2. Equity

As an equity-building process, ROADS centers Indigenous Peoples as equal partners in observing, data system governance, and knowledge production. In Phase I, EPs establish norms that support shared leadership, space, and resources with Indigenous members. Phase II advances equity by ensuring that Indigenous decision-making needs and societal priorities shape the definition of benefits. In Phase III, this principle emphasizes Indigenous data sovereignty and calls on EPs to align their information requirements with ethical standards such as Free, Prior, and Informed Consent (FPIC) and the CARE Principles.

3. Support Societal Benefits

The foundation of ROADS is the belief that observing should serve broadly shared societal needs. This principle is most evident in Phase II, where EPs must conduct a rigorous and transparent assessment of how better information can support outcomes like food security, infrastructure resilience, or disaster preparedness. Evaluation by the AP will look for evidence that benefits were defined with relevant partners like communities, not for them, and that the technical requirements developed in Phase III directly map back to these established benefit targets.

4. Build on What Exists

To address the current fragmentation of Arctic observing, EPs must actively connect with and leverage existing efforts. This is particularly relevant during Phase II and III, where EPs should develop a systems-level view of current capabilities and identify how their work integrates with global frameworks, such as Essential Climate or Ocean Variables. Documentation should clearly demonstrate how the EP's Shared Arctic Variables (SAVs) complement rather than duplicate existing networks and projects.

5. Step-by-Step Progress

The ROADS process is designed to be flexible, allowing ideas and priorities to emerge as relationships deepen. This principle guides the transition between all phases, encouraging EPs to move at a pace that allows for ongoing feedback loops with the AP and the broader community. The AP evaluates this progress not just by the completion of phases, but by how the EP incorporates feedback to strengthen their benefits statements and implementation strategies over time.

Foundational Practices

Central to the Arctic ROADS process are ethics - Indigenous, data, and fundamentally how we treat each other. Data ethics include [FAIR](#) and [CARE](#) principles, as well as consideration of Indigenous data sovereignty in regard to ownership, permissions, and control. As this field continues to develop, it's critical for researchers to communicate with the Indigenous communities they work with to fully understand and adhere to the preferred practices of those communities.

Several Indigenous groups in the Arctic have developed ethics and protocols for collaboration specifically with Indigenous Peoples. These include regional guidance (e.g. [Inuit Circumpolar Council](#)) and strategies (e.g. [National Inuit Strategy on Research](#)). Some universities have included these guidance in their ethical review processes (e.g. [University of Alaska Fairbanks' Institutional Review Board](#)). Often Indigenous partners will need approval from their own governance bodies, e.g. Indigenous/Tribal Councils or co-management bodies. These ethical protocols and bodies vary across the Arctic and can be layered and complex. Seek guidance from your university's ethical review committees and from your Indigenous partners prior to engaging in data collection, even if it is preliminary. It is the EP co-lead researchers' responsibility to understand the ethics, ensure they are followed, and complete required paperwork prior to engaging.

Free, Prior, and Informed Consent ([FPIC](#)) is a common ethical principle that has been expanded upon in regard to the UN's Declaration of the Rights of Indigenous Peoples. Free is without coercion, including deadlines and building competition between communities. Prior is at the inception of the project idea to support Indigenous priorities. Informed is supporting capacity and resources needed to have an understanding of the research and project. Consent is a continuous process that requires iterative decision-points and where consent can be withdrawn at any time without penalty.

Equity and inclusion of Indigenous Peoples are a core part of Arctic ROADS, as reflected in the Guiding Principles. This looks like Indigenous leadership within the Advisory Panel (AP) and Expert Panels (EPs). Co-production of knowledge is the gold standard within EPs, which is shared decision-making at every step of the process. Layered on top of co-production of knowledge are Indigenous ethics and engagement practices (e.g. [Ellam Yua conceptual model](#), Ellam Yua et al. 2022). Culturally-responsive engagement practices include supporting Indigenous sovereignty and self-determination, following decolonial approaches, navigating power dynamics, Indigenous control over Indigenous Knowledges and information, and supporting Indigenous languages and cultural revitalizations.

Supporting relationships and meaningful partnerships is a core function of EPs. To build relationships, EP facilitators and coordinators should seek mentorship from colleagues with relationships in their fields and in the areas they want to work in. EP leadership should prioritize the safety and comfort of Indigenous Peoples in setting and conducting meetings. An important step for those from academic backgrounds is networking at conferences and meetings that are well attended or led by Indigenous Peoples (e.g. Alaska Forum, Arctic Net, Greenland Science Week) and meetings focused on data-informed decision making (e.g. co-management councils). Understand the context potential Indigenous community partners are working in and how relevant data is needed and applied. Centering community priorities and needs will improve outcomes for those from academic backgrounds through greater relevance and insights of environmental changes.

Phase I – Initiate an Expert Panel

1. Goal of Phase I

The purpose of Phase I is to outline the proposed work of the Expert Panel (EP). The questions in 'Phase I' and 'Process' sections of the Workbook are meant to develop a shared vision and transparency between the EP and AP, as well as among the EP members.

2. Key Concepts

2.1 Formative Evaluation and Integrated Advising

In ROADS, formative evaluation is designed to guide and strengthen the work as it unfolds, helping EPs and the AP learn, adapt, and achieve the best possible outcomes rather than determine success or failure. ROADS uses integrated advising to achieve this so that EPs are supported by the AP throughout their work. An AP “Champion” helps track progress, provide connections, and support problem-solving. Structured feedback and formative evaluation from the AP at key points, as outlined in the Handbook, help EPs refine benefits, requirements, and implementation strategies (Phases II-IV).

2.2 Practices that support success
Effective EPs tend to:

- Start by building relationships, trust, and clarity of roles
- Write benefits in plain language and ensure understandability with users
- Co-design plans through shared working sessions and open consultation
- Be realistic and focused rather than exhaustive
- Address data ethics, governance, and interoperability from the start
- Document decisions and show how feedback shaped the work

2.3 Co-Production of Knowledge

The co-production of knowledge methodological approach has been identified as the gold standard for working with Indigenous Peoples and policy-makers. By definition it is shared decision-making at every step of the research project, including the design phase. This shared ownership increases relevance of the work and shared understanding of all members of the EP including Indigenous Knowleges, scientific information, operational expertise, and use of the resulting outputs of the EP. Co-production of knowledge is time consuming, which may not be practical for every EP, but the more you can make shared decision-making the better. Even if the EP decides to not follow co-production of knowledge process, but instead prioritizing certain phases for more involvement. A critical time period in the ROADS process for shared decision-making with in particular Indigenous Peoples would be during Phase I.

3. Outputs

In Phase I, the EP will develop these sections of the ROADS Process Workbook:

- Introduction
- Membership
- Applying the Guiding Principles

- Process Questions

The output from this phase is a Phase I proposal (or Concept Note) that will be submitted to the AP for evaluation and feedback.

4. Step-by-Step Instructions

For all instructions that follow, the numbers for each section of the workbook correspond directly to the numbers for those sections in the Workbook.

3.1 Fill out “Introduction to the Expert Panel (Phase I)” section

1. *Abstract of proposed EP [300 words]:* This abstract will be the shared overview of your EP. Focus on what the most important aspects are that you want people to know about.
2. *Overview of the proposed EP [1,000 words]:* The [Overview section in Workbook Phase I](#) should be just enough information to express the main points of the thematic focus. In the Process section, there are many questions related to how the EP will collaborate and make decisions, to ensure there is a shared vision among EP members. You will fill out the entire [Process section](#), including proposed work within Phase II-IV. You will revisit these Process questions every time you submit documentation of a Phase, supporting iterative improvements and course correcting as you go.
 1. *Scope:* Characterize the scope of the thematic focus area. The AP will review based on the EP’s perception of its scope. If the scope is too large to develop a strategic plan or too narrow to have wider shared benefit to the Arctic observing network, the AP will provide feedback for adjustment.
 2. *Societal Relevance:* Characterize the societal relevance of the EP thematic focus, which should be co-developed within the EP and prioritized for which areas are most important. For more narrow topics, e.g. salmon monitoring in Bristol Bay, the EP could compare observing networks in other regions to demonstrate wider shared benefit to the Arctic observing network. This is a high-level starting point to the deeper societal benefit work that will follow.
 3. *Purpose:* Describe the co-defined goals of the EP, including wider societal or policy impacts. As Arctic ROADS concerns observing and data systems, please characterize the goals to overcome perceived shortcomings in Arctic observing and data systems.
 4. *Target Audience:* Characterize who the EP recommendations will be developed for. These could be categories, i.e. national funders or Arctic researchers, but please try to be specific in identifying actual entities as much as possible.
 5. *Grounding Vision:* Characterize the vision of success for the EP. For example, do you already envision tangible outcomes that might emerge from this work in terms of specific types of investments in Arctic observing or data systems? Your vision may include potential products, services, or other outcomes from this work and their users or beneficiaries. This section is a useful place to cite literature or any preparatory workshops that have taken

place to support this work. NOTE: We recognize that ROADS is in place to develop these types of visions and you may not have a clear vision at this point, but we believe it is useful to have some grounding in tangible benefits that can be revisited and revised throughout the process.

3.2 Fill out “Phase I Process” section

Workbook 2.a. Membership of the EP: Provide the relevant information on the EP members in the provided table template. Feel free to add more rows or separate tables if there are distinct categories of members, e.g. facilitation group, steering group, or *ad hoc* members that will be called upon at certain times. The recommended EP size is 10-12 people. Please provide a brief justification if the total number is greater or less below the table. Lastly, please list any other parties providing input or feedback to the EP, e.g. *ad hoc* expertise called upon in meetings, presentations to Tribes, specific communities, professional networks/organizations, advisors, etc. This is a good place to think of the different audiences listed in Section 1.

Workbook 2.b. Applying Guiding Principles

Answer, to the best of the EP’s ability, How the group will apply each of the Guiding Principles (#1-5) to the work of your EP.

Workbook 2.c.1 Phase 1 process questions:

1. *How does the EP plan to convene and communicate?* e.g. regular virtual meetings, in person meetings of opportunity, etc. For communication, will it be monthly email updates, Slack or other communication method, phone calls, etc?
2. *Identify planned mechanisms through which broader input can be included in the work of the EP,* such as through open workshops or community meeting(s). Reference any engagement frameworks that will be used (e.g., [ICC EEE](#), [ITK-Canada](#), [Ellam Yua Co-Production of Knowledge](#), etc).
3. *How will the EP make decisions and record these decisions? What guidelines for participation do you plan to use or develop?* The goal for these questions is to facilitate developing a process that members feel is legitimate and fair, and most importantly transparent.
4. *Please provide confirmation that you have met the required ethical review boards, permitting, and approvals for the relevant research institution and partnering community requirements.* Provide any approval/permitting numbers, or confirmation that you did inquire about needed approvals and were deemed exempt. Human subject research regulations do vary between countries and institutions, so please do not make assumptions that approvals are not needed.
5. *Describe any relationship/relevance to other EPs.* Does this EP build upon or overlap with other EPs, where are the distinctions and boundaries?
6. *Expected timeline through the Integrated Advisory Process.* The timeline should include the expected dates of submission of each of the Phases to the AP with a 4-6 week turnaround for the AP evaluation and feedback at each stage.
7. *Briefly identify funding needs for the EP members and activities.* Who on the EP needs funding support for their work/contributions, and are those funding needs met? Is there funding available for in-person meetings and/or a community

workshop? Describe to the extent possible during the early stages of the EP to secure funding to meet these funding needs?

8. *How is the EP engaging the funders you imagine would be involved in the implementation of the EP recommendations and developing SAVs? Think back to your target audience and grounding vision for this question. Engaging those responsible for implementation during the ROADS process will increase their perceptions of legitimacy and the likelihood of operationalizing the recommendations.*

3.3 Fill out “Process” section (Phase II-IV) as proposed work

Workbook 2.c.2 The AP encourages the EP to fill out Phase II process questions in order to look ahead to the future of the work they will complete, understanding that these will be revised as part of the iterative process. This provides the AP an early opportunity to provide feedback on proposed Phase II work.

1. *Summarize the approach (e.g., method, deliberations, engagement, evaluation tools) taken to develop and assess societal benefit and develop use cases in Phase II of the EP’s work. As you are developing Phase I, this should be reflective of a draft proposal of the possible approach to gain early feedback from the AP.*
2. *Describe any specific benefit framework(s) used and how they were used in evaluation. Again, for Phase I, this is a draft proposed approach to get feedback from the AP. Refer to section 3.1, but some things to think about in Phase I is which frameworks and approaches you may want to follow based on Arctic observing generally or more topical frameworks, e.g. [Salmon Fisheries Well-Being Framework](#).*

Workbook 2.c.3 The AP encourages the EP to fill out Phase III process questions in order to look ahead to the future of the work they will complete, understanding that these will be revised as part of the iterative process. This provides the AP an early opportunity to provide feedback on proposed Phase III work. *This is not required at Phase I, but should be considered required for the Phase the EP is currently in.*

1. *Describe your approach to specifying requirements for each SAV. As your SAVs may span multiple existing specifications found in other variable-based frameworks, it is acceptable to adopt a different approach to requirements for each SAV or Sub-variable under this Expert Panel. [300 words]*
2. *Describe how the EP’s recommendations for observing system requirements “complement” and improve upon existing observing systems (Guiding Principle 3). [300 words]*
3. *Describe how the EP’s recommendations for data systems requirements described in this document “complement and integrate” existing data systems. For example, which data centers or producers have you conferred with in drafting these recommendations? (guiding Principle 3) [300 words]*
4. *Describe your approach to specifying data system requirements for each SAV. As your SAVs may span multiple existing data systems, it is acceptable to adopt a different approach to requirements for each SAV under this Expert Panel. This*

description will be evaluated based on how the Expert Panel is addressing things like open/accessible data and the requirements needed to respect data sovereignty.
[300 words]

Case Study: The Wildfire Expert Panel – Finland

In 2022, Finnish partners noticed that summer wildfires were intensifying and that scientific and emergency response data were scattered across agencies. The emerging team – researchers from Finnish Environment Institute (SYKE) and Finnish Meteorological Institute (FMI), Indigenous Sámi representatives, and civil-protection officers – met informally after an Arctic Observing Summit session.

They asked: *“Why is fire data so fragmented, and who actually needs it day-to-day?”*

This discussion led to a one-page statement of urgency: increasing wildfire risk, insufficient real-time data, and missing community input on preparedness. That single page became the nucleus of their Phase I proposal (previously referred to as a Concept Note) that eventually became the first Expert Panel to pilot the Arctic ROADS process.

Case Study: The Wildfire Expert Panel – Mapping Existing Efforts and Shared Benefits

The Wildfire EP catalogued Finnish Meteorological Institute satellite products, Arctic Council work on wildfire smoke, and Indigenous observing networks tracking burned areas.

They discovered extensive but disconnected data streams.

In a shared spreadsheet (later integrated into their Phase I proposal), they wrote benefits in plain language:

- Faster warnings for villages
- Improved air-quality advisories for reindeer herders
- Shared seasonal outlook for cross-border fire teams

This became their anticipated shared benefits list ([Workbook Section 3](#)) and guided later funding proposals.

Case Study: The Wildfire Expert Panel – Early Engagement and Trust-Building

The Wildfire EP held its first hybrid meeting in Rovaniemi in March 2023, co-hosted by the Finnish National Rescue Services and Sámi community liaisons. They applied the Workbook’s Principle “start with relationships, not deliverables.” Instead of slides, they opened with local stories about smoke visibility and livelihood impacts. This meeting cemented their partnership structure and ensured that Indigenous concerns were explicit from day one – this is documented in the [Workbook Section 2.c.1](#).

5. Submit the Workbook Phase I to the AP Champion

Once the EP has completed all of the sections above, the document produced is considered the EP's Phase I sections of the workbook. Submit that document to the AP by emailing it to your AP Champion. The AP Champion will share the document with the AP co-chairs and cc the EP co-leads. At this time, the EP should have identified one or two outside subject-matter experts (SMEs) who could serve as independent reviewers of your documentation. These reviewers should not be part of the EP or the Advisory Panel. The AP co-leads will email these individuals about providing early technical or thematic feedback to strengthen the draft before formal evaluation.

6. EP Check-in before moving to Phase II

The EP should ensure that all members agree that:

- The scope is clear and actionable.
- Indigenous and community leadership is present and funded.
- Existing efforts are acknowledged and this work complements them.
- Next-step meetings are scheduled and visible to partners.

Phase II – Define and Assess Shared Objectives (Societal Benefit Assessment)

1. Goal of Phase II

Phase II turns broad thematic EP goals into an explicit understanding of who stands to benefit from observing system improvements. It helps each EP explore, through information use cases, the societal benefits that improved observing and data systems could create. This phase provides a transparent structure for assessing relevance, value, and impact together with those most directly concerned.

2. Key Concepts

2.1 Shared Societal Benefits

Shared societal benefits describe the positive outcomes that improved observing and data systems can create for communities, decision makers, and society more broadly—such as safer infrastructure, healthier ecosystems, or better disaster preparedness. They help EPs clarify who benefits from improved information and why those benefits matter.

2.2 Information Use Cases

Information use cases are real-world scenarios that show how people use information to make decisions or take action. They connect broad societal benefits to specific needs by describing who uses the information, what they need it for, and what would improve if better data were available.

2.3 Shared Arctic Variables

Shared Arctic Variables are observable phenomena that multiple sectors agree are critical to monitor because they link scientific understanding with community and operational needs. They translate shared societal benefits and information use cases into concrete observing and data system priorities.

3. Outputs

In Phase II, the EP will develop these sections of the ROADS Process Workbook:

- [Section 2: Updated Process Description](#)
- [Section 3: Benefit Assessment Report](#)
- [Section 4: Information Use Case Summaries](#)

4. Step-by-Step Instructions

Completing Phase II of the ROADS process will deepen your EP's involvement and shared understanding of needed improvements in Arctic observing networks and data systems, with an emphasis on why these improvements are necessary from a broad range of societal perspectives. As with all aspects of the process, the following steps are recommended to

guide your process, not to be prescriptive. ROADS welcomes innovation from EPs and some divergence from the guide may be necessary.

4.1 Map EP thematic scope to societal needs

The first step in Phase II relates the Purpose, Scope and Vision you outlined in Phase I into tangible societal benefits. The high-level goals outlined in societal benefit frameworks (alternately described as impact, goals, security, or risk framework) provide a useful and comprehensive way to begin this work. Using a framework, versus a more *ad hoc* approach, adds rigor to this step in the process and provides a mechanism to link the impacts of your work to clearly articulate goals. We recommend that your EP begin with a review of relevant societal benefit frameworks including SAON's International Arctic Observations Assessment Framework (IAOAF; Box X).

Following this review, the EP may find an existing societal benefit framework that is a better fit than SAON's IAOAF for its needs. As societal benefits frameworks are often quite broad, we recommend that the EP prioritize a few specific areas for progress within an existing framework. Alternatively, an EP may choose to generate their own framework from the ground up (see Box Sea Ice EP). While more ambitious, this approach will assure that the EP has full ownership of the societal benefit framing. The group may find that a mixed approach is the best fit. However the group proceeds, the EP should recognize and articulate the specific role that observations and data play in supporting progress in priority societal benefit areas.

For research-specific objectives, the EP may want to reference the work of *Meadow and Owen* (2021) to articulate the specific ways that research translates into societal impact.

Action: Describe your EPs process to identify and assess societal benefits in [Workbook Section 2.C.2](#). Please include links or references as needed.

■ Case Study: The Wildfire Expert Panel – Community Co-Leadership

In the northern pilot region, Sámi participants emphasized the importance of traditional burn areas and changes in lichen growth after fires.

Their inputs shifted the benefit discussion toward ecosystem recovery and subsistence planning, adding dimensions missed by technocratic agencies.

The panel formally listed a Sámi co-chair in its records and credited this input in the Benefits Report

4.2 Map societal needs to information use cases

The societal benefit framework and priority areas identified in the previous step rely upon high quality information derived from observing, data and knowledge systems. For example, a key objective related to Disaster Preparedness in the IAOAF recognizes the need to “conduct risk assessments to inform disaster preparedness activities.” This objective suggests a tangible set of information products that a decision maker would rely on to meet this objective.

In this generative step, EPs will map the prioritized societal benefit areas from the previous step into one or more relevant scenarios - known as ‘information use cases’ - drawn from

the diversity of its EP's perspectives. Documented work should address both the current state and desired state of information needed to support use cases.

For each scenario, the EP should identify:

- **Users or user groups** (for example, hunters, municipal planners, ferry operators)
- **Decision or action** (what they must decide or do)
- **Information currently used** (including multiple knowledge systems)
- **Information desired for use** (including multiple knowledge systems)
- **What would improve** as a result of better observations

A possible template for this is filling in the blanks on this sentence:

As a [user or group], I want to [decision or action] in order to [what would improve]. [To do that, I currently have information about _____. I still desire information about _____]

You are not required to do that format exactly, but the more specific you are in describing the scenarios in which people would use information related to your theme, the easier the next steps will be.

As a new PhD student, I want to have data in order to work with on my project. [To do that, I need information about measurements of permafrost active layer thickness in Alaska since 2015.]

As a fisheries manager in Alaska, I want to inform limits to set for the upcoming fishing season. [To do that, I need information about how many salmon are in my particular region.]

As a _____, I want to do _____ in order to _____. [To do that, I need information about [wildfire]]

While this approach is a recommended ROADS practice based on use-centered design, EPs are welcome to develop their own methods to map from broad societal benefits to scenarios of data and information use.

Action: Complete the Information [Use Case Table](#) or document equivalent work.

Box: The International Arctic Observations Assessment Framework (IAOAF)

The International Arctic Observations Assessment Framework (IAOAF) was developed by Sustaining Arctic Observing Networks (SAON) and its partners to create an internationally agreed-upon set of benchmarks to evaluate the value of Arctic-relevant observations and structure a sustained, integrated pan-Arctic observing system. The IAOAF functions much like other global frameworks built around shared goals, such as the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), which unite diverse actors through common outcomes rather than similar methods. The framework provides a common language for describing societal benefit from

observations gathered across the Arctic. Because the Arctic influences global systems—for example, melting ice contributes to worldwide sea level rise—these benefits can extend far outside the region.

The framework is organized around 12 high-level categories called **Societal Benefit Areas (SBAs)**. These SBAs cover essential community concerns like Disaster Preparedness, Food Security, Human Health, Infrastructure and Operations, and Weather and Climate. Using a systematic approach, the framework breaks these 12 areas down into 163 objectives, linking observation systems to tangible services, research outcomes, and community activities. This structure helps partners identify which data inputs are critical for supporting life, economy, and environmental quality throughout the Arctic and beyond.

In practice, the IAOAF helps ROADS participants connect local priorities to a shared Arctic-wide picture of benefit and need.

Case Study: The Wildfire Expert Panel – Gathering Wildfire Use Cases

During spring 2023, the Wildfire EP ran a series of workshops with municipal authorities, rescue services, reindeer herders, and air-quality scientists.

Participants shared 15 use cases, including:

- Evacuation decision timing based on smoke plumes
- Forecast accuracy for fire-spread models
- Public health messaging during haze events

The EP realized that different agencies used incompatible data formats – a finding that later shaped their SAV requirements (listed in the Phase II Wildfires documentation).

4.3 Assess current and desired capabilities

In this step, the EP will systematically evaluate how well current observing and data systems support their relevant societal benefits and develop projections about how desired improvements to the systems will enhance societal benefit. This is an important step toward developing the initial [Vision](#) outlined in the EPs Phase I documentation. In this step the EP might identify novel targets for observation or innovative means for observing well-known targets. Improvements might entail better harmonization and dissemination of data from existing systems, enhanced deployments of new systems, or sustained support for community-led observers. Given that there are many ways to improve a system, this step assures that the recommended improvements generate broadly shared benefits, build off of existing efforts, and uphold process equity in rigorous and transparent ways.

Value tree assessment methods are well aligned with societal benefit assessment. They link observing and data systems via use cases to societal benefits. The IAOAF was designed for this use and several SAON partners have developed accessible tools to support this work (Box ? - US AON BENEFIT Tool, Case Study - FMI tool). Methods use expert elicitation to both link and understand the performance and importance of observations and data products to different information use cases. Value tree assessment tools support visualization, dialog and communication about the results of the EPs work. As with other aspects of ROADS, EPs are welcome to use these tools or adopt their own approach.

Action: Summarize the findings of your EP's Societal Benefit Assessment in Section 4. Question 1 linked [here](#)). Attach relevant reports and visualizations of your assessment to contribute to transparency and understanding of your work in your outputs.

Case Study: The Wildfire Expert Panel – Applying the Benefit Tool

Using the Workbook matrix, the Wildfire EP ranked benefits by “urgency + breadth.”

Top three were:

1. Improved real-time fire-spread forecasts (critical to public safety);
2. Integrated smoke and air-quality data for health alerts;
3. Cross-border data exchange to support resource sharing.

They documented scores in the Benefit Tool table and attached community comments verbatim – a practice highlighted in the 2024 Phase II Evaluation as a model of transparency.

4.4 Identify areas for progress through Shared Arctic Variable development

In the preceding steps, EPs will have developed a systematic understanding of needed improvements to Arctic observing and data systems and clearly articulated the benefits of addressing them. In this step, EPs evaluate how the needed improvements cluster around related observable phenomena like measurable sea ice characteristics or salmon enumeration. This effort moves the group from thinking about desired observing targets that expand shared societal benefits to collectively defining the observing and data system requirements needed to propel those advancements.

Action: Complete Questions 2-4 in Section 4. [Societal Benefit Assessment](#).

Case Study: The Wildfire Expert Panel – Identifying Candidate SAV

By late 2023, the Wildfire EP had narrowed its focus to four phenomena shared across sectors that were considered by the group for their role as SAVs:

1. Burned area extent
2. Fire severity index
3. Smoke and PM2.5 dispersion fields
4. Community health impacts

These became their “Candidate Shared Arctic Variables for Wildfire Preparedness”. The EP explicitly noted that these variables bridge scientific and community knowledge systems – precisely the goal of Phase II Step 6.

5. Check-in before moving to Phase III

(Process Workbook: Phase II “Ready to Proceed” checklist)

- Descriptions are written in plain language and tied to real decisions
- Priorities and processes reflect Indigenous and community leadership
- Process documentation explains who was engaged, what was heard, and how it shaped the results

Phase III – Develop Observing and Data Requirements

Goal of Phase III

Phase III turns ideas about benefits and use cases into specific requirements for observing and data systems. Expert Panels translate what has been learned in Phase II into clear, practical directions for what information is needed, where, and how it should be collected and shared. Turn the prioritized benefits and named phenomena into specific, actionable requirements for observations and data stewardship. Produce requirement tables, including both observation and data/information requirements. The goal of this phase is to document how meeting specific requirements for observing and data/information systems will facilitate the societal benefits identified in Phase II.

Concepts

Shared Arctic Variables (SAVs) are how the ROADS process organizes observing and information requirements. A SAV is something we can observe where information related to those observations is needed across a range of interests and use cases in the Arctic.

The definition of Shared Arctic Variables¹:

Shared Arctic Variables (SAVs) are a vital concept within the SAON Arctic ROADS process to support convergent planning around observable phenomena that lead to broadly shared benefits. The SAV concept is related to, but distinct from, essential variables such as those used by the global networks (e.g. Essential Ocean Variables of the Global Ocean Observing System). Both similarly use the term ‘variable’ in a very broad sense (see below). While pilot efforts are underway to demonstrate the SAON Arctic ROADS process, we provide this working definition of what we mean by an SAV.

- **Shared:** Developed through a process of co-design and sustained partnerships, inspired by an intersection of interests related to how observations will be used in support of broadly shared societal benefit.
- **Arctic:** A diversely defined region where specific phenomena and considerations drive observing requirements that are distinct from global requirements.
- **Variables:** Observable phenomena (from both scientific processes and Indigenous Knowledge Systems) that are critical for characterizing a system and its changes; parsed into more granular observable properties.
- In developing definitions for the SAVs identified, the EP may find that it wants to add greater detail through sub-level definitions. Following the practice of global networks, we recommend that these be referred to as “Sub-variables” of SAVs. You may also want to recommend that supporting variables, not directly tied to your SAV are also observed. These might relate to weather or climate drivers that add context and

¹ <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1ZGlzPezvJ0jYv3FIGiuMFpRwOyLKce4us4f7oIYxtng/edit?tab=t.0>

understanding to your SAV, but are not an inherent aspect of it as an ‘observable phenomenon’.

Definitions and Ontologies

The concept of data ontologies will prove important for establishing these definitions in good relationship with existing or future efforts. A data ontology is a vocabulary of concepts within a specific domain that demonstrates certain properties of the domain and the relationships between those properties. It is a structured framework used by the data management community that defines the concepts, relationships, and properties within a domain (e.g. cryospheric science), and how to organize, access, and understand the data within it. An example definition for “permafrost thickness”, taken from the Cryosphere Glossary (a data ontology for cryosphere) at the National Snow and Ice Data Center (<https://nsidc.org/learn/cryosphere-glossary>) would be “the vertical distance between the permafrost table and the permafrost base.” Other examples of relevant data ontologies can be found in the appendix on this topic.

For consistency, clarity and harmonization with other efforts, it is important that SAV definitions be tied, where possible, to existing definitions used by the observational community. In the documentation for the AP, we also ask the EP to indicate if you are a) using an existing definition (provide a reference for the ontology it comes from), b) extending an existing definition (provide a reference for the ontology), c) or creating a new definition (where applicable, describe how will you contribute or build an accessible ontology).

A data ontology is a vocabulary of concepts within a specific domain that demonstrates certain properties of the domain and the relationships between those properties. A useful general purpose definition of data ontology and its application to data science can be found here: <https://builtin.com/data-science/ontology>. The Semantics Working Group of the Arctic Data Committee has published this open letter on Promoting effective use of semantics in Polar science and operations. More specifically, the Working Group maintains this list of ontological resources specifically for the polar community to utilize.

A discussion of semantics in the context of Arctic data is found in Chong et al., which highlights the Ecosystem Ontology. Another relevant example is the Arctic Report Card Ontology.

3. Outputs

In Phase III, you will fill out several sections of the workbook:

- Phase III process questions, Workbook [Section 2.c.3](#)
- SAV definitions (Phase III), Workbook [Section 5](#)
- Observing requirements (Phase III), Workbook [Section 6](#)
- Information and data system requirements (Phase III), Workbook [Section 7](#)

4. Step-by-Step Instructions

4.1 Update the Information Use Case Summaries (Workbook Section 3)

For each of the information use cases/scenarios described in Phase II, the goal of Phase III is to detail the SAV specifications necessary for those observations to be useful for the

scenario(s) described. At the end of Phase II, the EP identified several use cases tied to bigger societal benefit. For each of these use cases, think about what information is needed. What questions are people trying to answer? These will help you define the observation requirements during this phase (Section 6). Update this section using the prompts in Section 3 and the preliminary information the EP developed in Phase I.

4.2 Shared Arctic Variables (Workbook Section 5)

In Phase II of Arctic ROADS, the EP identified potential SAVs (*Workbook Section 4. Societal Benefit Assessment*). In Phase III, you will refine and finalize the SAV(s), and clearly define what should be observed under each SAV with sufficient clarity to support the use cases and harmonization across diverse efforts.

For each SAV identified during Phase II (*Workbook Section 5*), review relevant data ontologies/ definitions as much as possible (see definitions in Appendix A.1.2 and Appendix A.2). From these, adopt or develop a plain language definition of the SAV(s) and/or sub-variables (*Table in Workbook Section 5*). If this definition is linked to an existing ontology, please describe. Record this work in the table provided in Section 5: SAV definitions (Phase III) in the Workbook.

Document the process you use to come to these definitions, e.g.:

Example of Table in Section 5. SAV definitions (Phase III) filled out by the HABs EP.

Shared Arctic Variable	Sub-Variables ¹	Plain Language Definition	Reference for this definition
Example: Harmful Algal Bloom Expert Panel			
e.g., "cyst beds"			
"toxin concentration"	ng/g of stx in tissues or water measured through HPLC		
	ng/g of doa in tissues or water measured through HPLC		

4.3 Observing Specifications/Requirements (Workbook Section 6)

For your Shared Arctic Variable(s), consider each information use case. In this step, we want to identify what makes observations "good enough" to fill that need. Specifications that may seem obvious to the information user are not necessarily obvious to an observer, and requirements may vary between use cases. For example, a "sea ice thickness" SAV would require measurements of both level ice thickness and ridge height for the use case of Indigenous hunters building trails out to the ice edge, but would only require level ice thickness measurements for the use case of climate modeling.

Observing requirements may include:

- Desired accuracy
- Spatial resolution

- Frequency/time resolution
- Spatial coverage of observations
- Observing mode (in situ versus remote sensing) if applicable
- Indigenous Knowledge and/or community observations
- Environmental and/or cultural footprint of observations
- Other requirements as needed

Add a quick paragraph about environmental footprint AND cultural/community footprint.

Additionally, consider whether one or more of the GCOS *Essential Climate Variables* (ECVs) or GOOS *Essential Ocean Variables* (EOVs) is contributing to this SAV. If yes, can the current [ECV requirements](#) or [EOV requirements](#) be used as an observing requirement specification? Each requirement should be briefly justified (one sentence may be sufficient, but more may be required for some information use cases).

Where appropriate, a range of requirements may be included. For example, climate models may require spatial resolution better than 25 km in a sea ice thickness product, but are unable to assimilate better than 1km resolution, resulting in a requirement for spatial resolution of 1-25 km.

For some observing requirements, there are ‘acceptable’ and ‘preferred’ specifications. For example, in wildfire management users of active burning area remote sensing products may prefer real-time updates but can work with 6 hour updates if that is all that is available.

Observing requirements may include additional information beyond the variable itself: contextual measurements may be required to meet the information needs (e.g., air temperature measurements supporting observations of coastal sea ice thickness informing ice breakup risk assessment).

The more detail available in the requirements, the better able observers are to meet the information needs previously identified in Phase II.

One approach to organizing observing requirements would be to fill out the following table for each *information use case* and SAV described in the previous sections. Not all the rows will be applicable to every scenario. You can organize this information in another way if it makes more sense. An example of what the table in Section 6 of the Workbook could look like is presented here:

SAV/ Information use case: Sea ice / Coast guard needs information on sea ice concentration to assess risk level for vessel traffic

Specification	Necessary to have (minimum acceptable for use)	Nice to have (optimal for use)
Observing mode: in situ, remote sensing, Indigenous Knowledge and/or community observations	Remote sensing : satellite	Remote sensing : satellite and/or aerial
Specific instrument type	Passive microwave instruments	

Spatial resolution	25km pixels	<1 km pixel size
Frequency/time resolution	Daily	Daily
Spatial coverage of observations	Whole Bering Sea/Chukchi Sea region	Coverage in high traffic areas
Tolerance for uncertainty	10-20% error is ok	<5% error
Other requirements	Must operate reliably in the winter, stormy weather	

4.4 Information and Data System Requirements (Section 7)

In addition to the requirements for observations themselves, information users need to be able to access that data in ways that are appropriate for the scenario.

EPs should have one or more members who have expertise in data systems and can help with translating plain-language information needs into data requirements. If your EP does not, consult the AP to help make connections with the data management community.

Requirements for data management should generally be consistent with the Statement of Principles and Practices for Arctic Data Management (IASC, 2013), FAIR Principles (Wilkinson et al., 2016), CARE Principles (Research Data Alliance International Indigenous Data Sovereignty Interest Group, 2019), and relevant Indigenous guidance. How these different concepts apply may vary depending on the context of the information needs. For example, information use cases that rely on Indigenous Knowledge and community observations may require closer adherence to the CARE principles. Information use cases within the scientific community, like for climate modeling applications, may require specific metadata standards and formats in addition to the FAIR principles.

Data requirements may include:

- Production and dissemination of higher order products from observations
- Data availability and access requirements (FAIR principles)
- Metadata requirements
- File formats (incl. data structures, tables, variables, recordings/photos, etc)
- Vocabularies and/or semantic technologies
- Alignment with data requirements for global variables (ECV, EOVs, GBON, GCOS, GOOS, WMO, etc)
- Indigenous data sovereignty requirements (CARE principles)

The data management community has developed a more detailed list of potential data requirements (see [Appendix 2](#)).

One possible approach for identifying data requirements for the different ways observations related to your SAV may be used is to walk through the FAIR and CARE principles for each scenario. For each principle, ask “What does [this principle] mean in the context of this scenario?” and fill in the following table, identifying both what that requirement would mean to the information user and what would be necessary on the data provider side to make it possible. For that use case, highlight the most relevant requirements as they relate to the way information is used in support of societal benefits. Not all principles will be relevant to all use cases.

Principle	General Definition	User's requirements for information access	What data systems are necessary to meet those requirements?
Timely	Data should be available without unnecessary delay.		
Findable	Research data should be easy to find		
Accessible	Data should be accessible under specific conditions, which may include restrictions. For example, private data can be FAIR if the steps to access it are clear.		
Interoperable	Data should be able to be exchanged and used across different systems and applications.		
Reusable	Data should be reusable and become as valuable as possible.		
Collective benefit	Indigenous Peoples should benefit from the data, and the research should align with the community's goals and needs.		
Authority to control	Indigenous Peoples should have the agency to make decisions about how they are represented in the data and how the data is governed.		
Responsibility	Researchers are accountable to Indigenous communities and must be able to demonstrate how their use of the data benefits Indigenous peoples.		
Ethics	Indigenous rights and wellbeing should be the primary concern at all stages of the data lifecycle.		

Additional discussion of CARE principles is available at the Global Indigenous Data Alliance website: <https://www.gida-global.org/care>

The idea of this phase is to link societal benefits, through use cases/scenarios, to requirements for observations and data/information availability. Data and information product requirements should, similar to the observation requirements, reflect what is needed in order to achieve the benefits identified in Phase II. Some requirements or specifications may be labeled as “preferred” (wants) rather than “acceptable” (needs), and some things may not apply to every information use case.

An example of what that table could look like is here:

SAV/Information use case: Sea ice concentration / Coast guard needs information on sea ice concentration to assess risk level for vessel traffic

Categories of requirements	User’s requirements for information access	What data systems are necessary to meet those requirements?	Nice to have
Timely	Data is available within 12 hours latency	Processing pipeline requirements	Data is available within 2 hours latency
Findable	Access does not change without a lot of warning	Stable API for access	Web viewer
Accessible	Consistent file format – process is set up once and used daily for years	Stable API for access, file format does not change	n/a
Interoperable	Can be compared to other data/information	Processing makes a quicklook image	Uses the same spatial grid as another popular product
Reusable	n/a	n/a	n/a
Collective benefit	No restrictions on distributing data/products	CC License or equivalent	n/a
Authority to control	n/a	n/a	n/a
Responsibility	n/a	n/a	n/a
Ethics	Potential observation/ data errors are flagged : bad data can put lives at risk.	QC processing runs in parallel with data processing	n/a

Following each table, briefly comment on the feasibility of reaching these requirements. Are there data and information systems that already meet these requirements? Are there important gaps?

As in previous phases, the EP is asked to identify two reviewers external to the EP that the AP will contact about reviewing the documentation. The ROADS AP Champion for the EP will be in touch with these potential reviewers regarding providing feedback on the documentation.

Submit the Workbook with the completed Phase III sections (6 and 7) and updated Phase I/II sections (if needed) to your AP Champion, who will submit to the appropriate contacts on the AP . The detailed steps of the Integrated Advisory Process, illustrating how the EP and AP will interact for evaluating Phase III are [here](#). Following the AP and any external review, ROADS Process Workbook(s) will be shared broadly with the SAON Board, relevant communities, observers, and information users.

4.6 Update Workbook Section 2.a-c - the Process section

Please continue to build the partnerships and identify linkages that support the Guiding Principles during your work. This Phase of ROADS is well-suited to a workshop that draws in a broader audience for your SAV(s). Document how your EP upheld the guiding principles during Phase III process questions in Section 2.c. in the [workbook](#). Process questions for Phase II-III (2.C.2, 2.C.3) should be updated and revised as needed.

Be sure to describe how you identified requirements (both for observing and information/data systems) in the workbook process description, Section 2.C.3. Your response might look something like this:

SAV / use case	Requirements Identification Approach
Fast Ice Thickness / Modelling	Our EP deemed it most effective to extend the requirements of the GOOS EOV for sea ice to include more detailed requirements for shore fast ice thickness; we will follow the same observing system specifications that are outlined here: https://gooscean.org/document/17464
Fast Ice Thickness / Indigenous hunters accessing ice edge	We leveraged a series of community meetings held in several Arctic Alaska villages between 2018-2023 where hunters and elders shared their experiences and concerns with a changing ice environment.
Ice age / Indigenous community travel safety decision making	Our group deemed it most effective to develop our own format for these requirements drawing on a co-production of knowledge approach with the IK holders on EP. We will refer to the ontologies and data formats in the SIKU platform for our requirements.
Salmon Abundance	Our EP participated in two workshops hosted by the Arctic Data Center and including other key data providers in the salmon sphere. The final report is here. We have designed a data portal that will address FAIR and CARE principles, etc.

5. Check-in before moving to Phase IV

(Workbook: Phase III “Ready to proceed” checklist)

- Every requirement is traceable back to a named benefit and use case
- Requirements are specific enough that observers can implement them

- Data care and sharing rules are written in plain language and agreed by partners

Phase IV – Develop Implementation Strategies

(see Process Workbook: “Phase IV – Implementation plan / Roles & responsibilities / Review and adaptation”)

Phase IV turns defined requirements into an achievable plan for action. Expert Panels design practical strategies for carrying out the observing and data activities described in Phase III.

1. Goal of Phase IV

Turn requirements into an agreed plan of action that people and organizations can carry out and sustain. Produce a full implementation plan with roles, schedules, funding paths, coordination with existing efforts, and built-in review.

(Workbook: Phase IV overview & outputs)

2. Concepts

3. Outputs

4. Step-by-Step Instructions

Complete Section 8. Implementation Strategy of the Workbook.

Build the plan from the tables

For each requirement cluster from Phase III, translate rows into actions (*Workbook: Plan-from-requirements guide*):

- **What will be done**
- **Where and when** (sites and schedule)
- **By whom** (named organizations and community partners)
- **With what support** (funding, staff time, in-kind resources)
- **How results will be shared with users**

Keep each action traceable back to a benefit.

Design the work program

- Organize actions into a timeline with milestones. (*Workbook: Timeline & milestones sheet*)
- Identify quick-start pilots and longer-term build-outs.
- For each milestone, state what evidence will show progress (for example, *first season of measurements at three crossings; monthly sharing with travel safety coordinators*).

(Workbook: “What success looks like” prompt)

Confirm partnership and governance

- Write a simple table of roles and responsibilities: convening team, community leads, operational partners, data stewards, evaluation support. (*Workbook: Roles & responsibilities table*)
- Describe how decisions will be made and how disagreements will be handled. (*Workbook: Governance notes*)
- Include how participation costs will be covered fairly. (*Workbook: Participation resourcing prompt*)

Resource the plan

- List what is needed for each action (financial, staff, equipment, travel, meeting time). (*Workbook: Resourcing table*)
- Note confirmed contributions and where additional support is still needed.
- Identify co-funding and alignment opportunities with existing programs. (*Workbook: Alignment & co-funding prompts*)

Coordinate with existing networks

- Map how the plan connects with current efforts so that platforms and methods can be shared and duplication avoided.
- Write down specific points of alignment (for example, shared stations, shared protocols, shared training). (*Workbook: Network alignment map*)

Embed review and adaptation

- Schedule regular check-ins to ask: *Is this doing what people need? What should change?*
- Decide how feedback from communities and users will be gathered and acted on.
- Keep the decision log active and visible

(*Workbook: Review & adaptation checklist*)

Outputs (Phase IV)

- **Final Implementation Plan** (Workbook structure): actions, partners, sites, timelines, resources, sharing pathway, review plan
- **Set of agreed shared variables for this effort** (the phenomena and measures that the partners commit to) (*Workbook: Variables confirmation step*)
- **Recommendations for integrating results with the wider Arctic ROADS community** (where results will be presented, how methods and lessons will be shared) (*Workbook: Integration notes*)

Quality Check for Completion of the Arctic ROADS Process

(*Workbook: Phase IV “Ready to implement” checklist*)

- Every action is linked to a requirement and a benefit.
- Roles, sites, and timelines are specific; partners named and have agreed.

- Resources are identified realistically, with clear next funding steps.
- Review moments and adaptation routes are built into the plan.

CONGRATS!

Evaluation and Continuous Improvement

(see Process Workbook: “Evaluation cycle / Decision log / Learning notes / Public-facing summaries”)

Evaluation is not a separate, one-time event; it is part of every phase.

At each stage, use the Process Workbook prompts to record:

- **What was tried and why** (the decision log)
- **Who was involved and how** (participation and support provided)
- **What changed as a result of feedback** (before/after notes in documents)
- **What to keep and what to adjust next time** (short learning notes at the end of each phase)

Share summaries widely. This transparency is how the Arctic ROADS community builds trust and avoids repeating mistakes. It is also how new groups learn quickly from those who went before them.

(Workbook: Evaluation prompts & sharing guidance)

APPENDICES

Appendix 1: Example outline for an Expert Panel Terms of Reference (charter)

Use this as a starting template when a new Expert Panel forms:

1. Purpose and scope

- Plain-language statement of the challenge and the widely shared benefits the panel will deliver
- Thematic/regional/issue focus and what is *in* and *out* of scope

2. Guiding Principles and commitments

- How equitable participation of Indigenous Peoples will be ensured and resourced
- How the panel will complement and integrate existing efforts
- How stepwise, flexible development will be practiced (including how scope may evolve)

3. Membership and roles

- Panel leads: responsibilities and time commitments
- Panel members: categories (Indigenous experts, community practitioners, researchers, managers, data stewards, funders/implementers)
- Processes for adding members and recognizing contributions

4. Engagement and ethics

- Plans for respectful relationship-building, consent processes, and data governance
- How Indigenous knowledge and languages will be supported and protected

5. Work plan and milestones (linked to ROADS phases)

- Near-term milestones (relationship-building, benefits articulation)
- Mid-term milestones (requirements and candidate SAVs)

- Later milestones (implementation strategies and alignment with programs)

6. Deliverables

- Benefits statements, requirements tables, candidate SAV descriptions
- Draft implementation strategy with partnerships and pathways to action
- Documentation of engagement and evaluation responses

7. Coordination and evaluation

- How the panel will coordinate with the Advisory Panel, including touchpoints and “Champion” support
- How feedback and independent review will be addressed and recorded

8. Sustainability

- Plans for maintaining relationships, updating requirements, and evolving the roadmap over time
- Funding and support needs, and how they will be pursued

Appendix 2: Possible data system requirements

The core goal of phase III is determining what the needs are for the information users: we need to be careful with the data requirements guidance that they (a) meet the needs of information users and (b) help those groups integrate with the broader data world. The following list includes considerations that may be relevant to data systems for an SAV:

1. Relevant data definitions and structure. Please describe these in terms of
 - a. Data structures (dimensions of variables), temporal, spatial, semantics.
 - b. Data tables and their relationships
 - c. Variables (columns): Their name and type (number, text, categories)
 - d. Vocabularies: Would category variables need to be supported by vocabularies? Are they already existing, or should they be developed (IV)? And are they available through semantic technologies?
 - e. Would there be a need to organize media files (recordings, video, etc.)
 - f. Do we need additional experts involved to help inform what data management, standards, and requirements looks like in this context? (It is possible to bring in people for a phase or two and not necessarily commit to the entire process)
 - g. Are these data structures/descriptions already aligned with existing standards?
 - h. Are there data (Indigenous data?, local data?, scientific data?) that can not be described in terms of the above?
2. Data systems and their management
 - i. Are the described data already organised in existing systems?(IV: If systems are not existing -> recommended systems must be developed)
 - j. If yes, are these systems managed in agreement with the
 - i. FAIR principles? Relevant questions are: Are standards used for this, like system interaction, Are metadata well described and according to relevant standards
 - ii. CARE principles?
 - iii. IASC Statement of Principles and Practices for Arctic Data Management?
 - k. If yes, is ownership, permits, attribution, and licensing of data understood/described?
 - l. If yes, Is there a well-described route of data from observing/sampling sites and to the data systems?
3. Relationship with the global variables(ECV, EOVS, GBON, GCOS, GOOS, WMO, etc)
 - a. Are the proposed SAVs related to global variables?
 - b. If yes, do they share specifications? Completely or partially?
 - c. (IV If yes, how do we implement the links to the relevant global systems?)
4. Data analysis, products, services
 - a. What data products will be produced
 - b. Who are the users/consumers of data products?
5. Information dissemination
 - a. How are data products made available to consumers?

6. User Engagement, Feedback and/or future co-production/co-design opportunities
 - a. Metrics / tracking
 - b. Revisit benefits tool to map value and social impact